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A STUDY OF EFFECT OF FAMILY CLIMATE ON MENTAL HEALTH OF RURAL AND URBAN B.ED. TEACHER-TRAINEES

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees in relation to their locality. Descriptive survey method was used for this study. Sample consisting 160 B.Ed. teacher-trainees was selected by using random sampling technique from four B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district. Family Climate Scale developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019) and Mental Health Inventory developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D. Helode (2008) used for data collection. Data was analyzed using Mean, S.D. and ANOVA (F-test). Finding reveals that there is significant effect of family climate on mental health of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher trainees on some dimensions and there was no significant interactions effect of different dimension of family climate and locality on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Keywords: Family Climate, Mental Health, Locality, B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Introduction:

The family is traditionally seen as the basic foundation of society. Generally, family can be seen as a group of people who have biological, emotional or legal ties to each other. A family is a child's first experience of relationships generally occurs within the family. It is a small intimate group of basic setting within which most children come in contact with society where they learn how to behave within a society and outside world. Family is the fundamental group of society which provides the natural environment for the growth and well being of all its members. The rising incidence of behavioural problems among adolescents demonstrates that some families are unable to cope with the increasing stresses they are experiencing. It is more important to have a harmonious

family climate. Psychologists have consistently proved that the proper development of the child is impossible without a good family climate or home environment.

Family as a social unit is an important determinant for shaping one's mental capacities along with their physical and social structure. The family climate is influenced by a number of factors like the nature of families' constellation, number of family members, marital relationship, parental employment and income, sibling relationship and socio-economic and religious background of the family. The family climate processes a certain consistency by which there is an impact of the same basic values, individuals, material objects etc. on the family members.

Mental health is an important determinant of one's integrated personality and balanced behaviour, identified on the basis of the level of his/her adjustment to own self, others and environment (Kaur *et al.*, 2015). A mentally healthy individual can adjust properly with environment, family and contribute for the society's progress and betterment (Lewkan, 1993). Mental health is the adjustment of human being with the world and also with one another to the maximum of effectiveness and happiness. It is the ability to maintain socially considerate behaviour, a happy disposition, an even temper and alert intelligence (Meninger, 2004).

Formal definition of locality is "A small area of country or city is called locality." These are two types of locality urban and rural. Urban areas have many facilities like transport, electricity, safe & clean drinking water, many schools, colleges and universities, coaching facilities etc. Rural areas have not proper facilities of citizens/people. So rural areas are less developed than urban areas.

Family climate plays an important role in every field of student's life. In this specific context the present research will be undertaken to specifically provide empirical answers to these questions like what is the role of family climate on the mental health of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees. A study was conducted on the mental health of secondary school students in relation to family climate by Singh and Devi (2018). Findings of this study revealed that there was a significant positive relationship of mental health with family climate. Similarly, Shivanae (2011) reported a significant difference of family climate and mental health of tribal and urban secondary school students.

Review of related literature reveals that various studies have been conducted on family climate and mental health in relation to various variables such as academic achievement, anxiety, life-satisfaction, occupational aspiration, intelligence, adjustment, adolescent-period etc. But it was found that no study has been conducted on the effect of family climate on the mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees in relation to locality. Hence the researcher has decided to undertake the study of the effect of family climate on the mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees in relation to locality.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To explore the effect of different dimensions of family climate on the mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

- To explore the effect of different dimension of family climate on mental health of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
- To study the interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and locality on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Hypothesis of the Study:

- There is no significant effect of different dimensions of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
- There is no significant effect of different dimensions of family climate on mental health of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
- There is no interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and locality on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Research Design & Methodology:

The researcher used descriptive survey method. Population of the present study consists of all the teacher-trainees of B.Ed. colleges affiliated to M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly. Sample of 160 teacher-trainees of four B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district selected with the help of simple random sampling techniques. **Family Climate Scale (FCS)** developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019) and **Mental Health Inventory (MHI)** developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D. Helode (2008) were used for the study. Data were analysed using Mean, S.D., and F-test (ANOVA).

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of different dimension of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table 1.1: Descriptive statistics of mental health of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Dimensions of Family Climate	Family Climate Group	Locality	N	Mean	S.D.
1. COHESION	Good FC	R	8	21.50	3.665
		U	12	23.75	4.731
	Average FC	R	41	22.17	3.270
		U	70	22.36	3.920
	Bad FC	R	11	20.64	3.695
		U	18	19.61	3.328
2. EXPRESSIVENESS	Good FC	R	1	21.00	0
		U	7	23.00	3.559
	Average FC	R	44	21.86	3.689
		U	67	22.00	4.369

	Bad FC	R	15	21.67	2.582
		U	26	21.85	3.461
3. CONFLICT	Good FC	R	2	21.00	5.657
		U	7	26.14	4.298
	Average FC	R	48	21.94	3.411
		U	68	22.04	4.031
	Bad FC	R	10	21.30	3.268
		U	25	20.84	3.472
4. ACCEPTANCE AND CARING	Good FC	R	0	0	0
		U	8	23.88	5.222
	Average FC	R	44	21.82	3.473
		U	68	22.15	3.986
	Bad FC	R	16	21.75	3.276
		U	24	21.08	3.833
5. INDEPENDENCE	Good FC	R	2	24.00	1.414
		U	5	24.80	4.324
	Average FC	R	27	22.63	3.712
		U	40	22.62	4.488
	Bad FC	R	31	20.94	2.988
		U	55	21.35	3.612
6. ACTIVE-RECREATIONAL ORIENTATION	Good FC	R	11	22.64	3.107
		U	24	24.71	3.581
	Average FC	R	32	21.53	3.698
		U	60	21.38	3.945
	Bad FC	R	17	21.76	3.052
		U	16	20.44	3.577
7. ORGANIZATION	Good FC	R	21	21.38	2.500
		U	38	22.21	4.749
	Average FC	R	18	23.67	3.481
		U	36	22.33	3.389
	Bad FC	R	21	20.62	3.556
		U	26	21.35	3.949
8. CONTROL	Good FC	R	8	23.13	2.232
		U	14	23.71	4.514

	Average FC	R	31	21.87	4.105
		U	50	22.38	3.806
	Bad FC	R	21	21.19	2.421
		U	36	20.89	4.055

Two way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-1. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-1.2

Table 1.2: Summary of ANOVA (Effect of different dimensions family climate on mental-health of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees).

Dimension	Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean squares	F-Ratio	Result
1.	Cohesion	109.90	2	54.95	3.93*	Significant
	Locality	5.061	1	5.061	0.362	Non Significant
2.	Expressiveness	0.91	2	0.45	0.30	Non Significant
	Locality	24.172	1	24.172	6.278*	Significant
3.	Conflict	37.93	2	18.96	1.35	Non Significant
	Locality	28.029	1	28.029	3.995*	Significant
4.	Acceptance & Caring	42.66	2	21.33	1.45	Non Significant
	Locality	0.806	1	0.806	3.55*	Significant
5.	Independence	45.57	2	57.78	4.06*	Significant
	Locality	1.788	1	1.788	3.46*	Significant
6.	Active recreational orientation	131.52	2	65.76	4.88*	Significant
	Locality	1.180	1	1.180	0.88	Non Significant
7.	Organization	97.64	2	48.32	3.4*	Significant
	Locality	0.205	1	0.205	1.84	Non Significant
8.	Control	90.14	2	45.07	3.24*	Significant
	Locality	1.959	1	1.959	2.94*	Significant

From Table 1.2, 'F' value for Cohesion, Independence, Active recreational orientation, organization and Control is 3.93, 4.06, 4.88, 3.4 and 3.24 respectively which is found to be significant ($p < 0.05$) for $df (2, 158)$ for the main effect of these dimensions of family climate on Mental health of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees. The significant F-value on these dimensions shows that family climate affects the mental health of students. Thus, the hypothesis (H1) - "There is no

significant effect of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees ” is rejected on these dimensions viz, Cohesion, Independence, Active recreational orientation, organization and Control and it is accepted on dimensions Expressiveness, Conflict and Acceptance & caring.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of different dimension of family climate on mental health of Rural and Urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

From Table 1.2, ‘F’ value for Expressiveness, Conflict, Acceptance & caring, Independence, and Control is 6.278, 3.995, 3.55 and 3.46 and 2.94 respectively which is found to be significant ($p < 0.05$) for $df(2, 158)$ for the main effect of these dimensions of family climate on Mental health of Rural and Urban B.Ed. Teacher Trainees. The significant F-value on these dimensions shows that family climate affects the mental health of Rural and Urban students. Thus, the hypothesis (H1) - “There is no significant effect of family climate on mental health of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher trainees” is rejected on these dimensions viz, Expressiveness, Conflict, Acceptance & caring, Independence, and Control. It is accepted on dimensions Cohesion, Active recreational orientation and Organization.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and locality on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Two way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-2. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-2.1

Table 2.1 summary of ANOVA (Interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and locality on mental-health B.Ed. teacher-trainees).

Dimensions	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean of squares	F-Ratio	Result
1.	Cohesion*locality	30.393	2	15.196	1.087	N.S.
2.	Expressiveness*locality	2.944	2	1.472	0.098	N.S.
3.	Conflict*locality	41.359	2	20.679	1.472	N.S.
4.	Acceptance and Caring*locality	6.999	1	6.999	0.477	N.S.

5.	Independence *locality	1.984	2	0.992	0.070	N.S.
6.	Active- Recreational Orientation *locality	47.287	2	23.644	1.755	N.S.
7.	Organization *locality	36.421	2	18.211	1.269	N.S.
8.	Control*locality	5.895	2	2.947	0.206	N.S.

The above table shows that null hypothesis “There is no significant interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and locality on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees” is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. It may be concluded that the main effect of family climate on mental health is independent of the effect of locality.

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